

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Impact of Exchange Rate on Foreign Reserves and Diaspora Remittances in Nigeria: 2015 – 2022**Okolie, Paschal I. P. PhD^{1*}, Osam, M. PhD² and Ezeamama, M. C. PhD³**¹*Department of Management, Finance and Accounting, University of America, Curacao*²*Department of Banking and Finance, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Agbani, Nigeria.*³*Department of Accounting and Finance, Spiritan University Nneochi, Abia State, Nigeria****Corresponding Author: Okolie, Paschal I. P. | of Management, Finance and Accounting, University of America, Curacao****ABSTRACT**

Nigeria as Africa's leading economy and an emerging country has huge potentials for diaspora remittances as they are spread all over the world. They are amongst the most educated and entrepreneurial migratory groups with their median household incomes standing at \$62,351 compared to the US national income average of \$57,617 as of 2015. However, despite the phenomenal increase in diaspora remittances to Nigeria, the exchange rate and the huge foreign exchange reserves have not benefitted the financial stability of Nigerian families. In view of the above, this study sought to empirically investigate the impact of foreign exchange rate on foreign exchange reserves and diaspora remittances received in Nigeria for the period, 2015 – 2022. The specific objectives are to investigate the impact of foreign exchange rates (FER) on the foreign reserves (FOR) and to examine the impact of foreign exchange rates (FER) on diaspora remittances (DPR) of Nigeria, for the period under review. We employed ex-post facto research design, gathered all the relevant data from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) for the period 2015 – 2022 and utilized multiple regression equation for this study. We adopted the ADF model to address the Unit root issues and then employed the dynamic ARDL model bounds tests to regress the dependent variable on the two independent variables. Ramsey regression error specification test was used to determine whether there is a functional form misspecification in the ARDL model used and we found that the model is correctly specified. From our study, we found that Foreign Exchange Rates have mixed effect on Foreign Reserves and Diaspora Remittances in Nigeria for the period, 2015 -2022 and concluded that the Nigerian economy has been bedeviled by several issues that require appropriate macro-economic policy remediation which should be addressed by adopting all or some of the recommendations adduced. We therefore recommend that the apex regulatory institution in Nigeria (CBN) should ensure the involvement of larger numbers of banks and other financial institutions in the inward transfer of diaspora remittances, among others.

Keywords: Exchange Rate; Foreign Reserves; Diaspora Remittances; Nigeria

Introduction

Nigeria, Africa's leading economy and an emerging country with huge potentials, has an ever-growing, highly educated and entrepreneurial population. The Nigerian diaspora is spread all over the world – from the United States of America (US) to the United Kingdom (UK), South Africa to the United Arab Emirates (UAE) and can even be found in European nations such as Italy and Spain. As per industry reports, Nigerians in the US are amongst the most educated and most entrepreneurial migratory groups, with their median household income standing at **\$62,351**, compared to the national average of **\$57,617** as of 2015 (Knomad, 2019).

China, which holds more than \$3 trillion of its assets in foreign currency, is the nation with the greatest foreign exchange reserve. They hold the majority of their reserves in US dollars. One of the benefits of these is that since the majority of international trade is conducted in US dollars, it makes it simpler to carry out. As of March 25, 2022, the US had foreign exchange reserves at \$247 billion, while China had reserves worth over \$3 trillion. Russia had \$630 billion in foreign exchange reserves as of February 2022, held primarily in US dollars, like the rest of the globe. However, some of the reserves are also kept in gold. Africa Market Forces, 2022). The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) expanded its involvement in the foreign exchange market in October 2022, depreciating its external reserves by \$866.2 million or 2.26%, from \$38.255 billion when it entered the month under review to \$37.39 billion.

By October 31, 2022, the country's foreign exchange buffer had declined by \$3.13 billion, or 7.73%, from \$40.5 billion to \$37.39 billion. Analysts bemoaned the declining inflow from crude oil sales, among other factors, and attributed the decline in external reserves to increasing intervention by the CBN bank in the retail Secondary Market

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Intervention Sales (SMIS) and Investors & Exporters (I & E) foreign exchange windows to stabilize the naira exchange rate.

They claimed that despite an increase in world oil prices, the Niger-Delta oil theft and production issue had slowed the expansion of the external reserves. Tajudeen Olayinka, CEO of Wyoming Capital & Partners, commented that the decline is a sign that external reserves have been added to only partially or insufficiently. He stressed that crude oil exports are the sole significant source that contributes to foreign reserves, and as Nigeria is unable to satisfy its OPEC output quota, external reserves would continue to experience such levels of insufficiency and inappropriateness (Tokede, 2022).

The **external reserves** in September, 2022 had dropped by \$740.26million or 1.9% to **\$38.28billion** amid the CBN's \$265 million intervention to airlines operating in the country to settle outstanding ticket sales. A total of \$230 million had been provided by the CBN as a special foreign exchange intervention, and another \$35 million had been made available through a retail SMIS auction. In response to unremitted payments for outstanding ticket sales, Emirates and other foreign airlines operating in Nigeria withdrew their services. However, the external reserves were hovering around \$40 billion on average in January 2022 and then fell to \$39 billion in three straight months (February through April) before rising to \$38 billion in May 2022. According to CBN's records, it was constant at \$38 billion in June and concluded at \$39.16 billion on June 30, 2022. Africa Market Forces, 2022).

The external reserves were still at \$38 billion in September 2022 but fell to \$37 billion in October. The CBN stated that the international reserves continued to be higher than the benchmark of three months of import cover in its second quarter (Q2) economic report. In contrast to the US\$39.28 billion at the end of March 2022, the CBN reports that the international reserves were \$39.22 billion at the end of June 2022. 7.2 months' worth of imports of both goods and services or 9.1 months' worth of imports of just goods may be covered by the foreign reserves. The CBN had \$37.98 billion (96.85%) of the external reserves, followed by the FG with \$1.20 billion (3.06%), and the Federation with the remaining \$0.04 billion (0.09%). The US Dollar made up \$30.06 billion (76.6%) of the total amount, followed by Special Drawing Rights (\$5.05 billion, 12.9%), Chinese Yuan (\$3.6 billion, 9.3%), GBP (\$0.22 billion, 0.6%), and Euros (\$0.25 billion, 0.6%). The remaining amounts were made up of various currencies. The price of crude oil in October 2022 also reflected the reduction in foreign reserves. The CBN estimates that the price of daily crude oil peaked in October 2022 at \$97.31 per barrel and then fell to \$96.81 (Tokede, 2022).

Remittances have been defined severally. Tewolde (2005), describes diaspora remittances monetary and non-monetary items that migrants earn while working abroad and later send back to their families living in their homeland(country). At the micro economic level, diaspora remittances can upgrade the financial status of individual households (family financial stability) and significantly improve their quality of life and accessibility to social benefits. From an economic perspective, diaspora remittances can fuel economic productivity, promote entrepreneurship and drive technological advancements. Worker's remittances consist of goods or financial instruments transferred by migrants living and working abroad to residents of the home economies of the migrants (Englama, 2007).

Diaspora remittances are limited to transfers made by workers who have stayed in foreign economies for at least one year while transfers from migrants that are self-employed are excluded from the computation. (IMF, 1999). However, despite the phenomenal increase in diaspora remittances and rise in international money transfers to Nigeria and Africa in general, the average cost for these money transfers to Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) remains the highest in the world. The cost to send diaspora remittances to Africa is relatively high at about 8.96%, according to a World Bank Report, even though the worldwide average cost of remittances is 6.82% as of the final quarter of 2019. (PwC, 2019).

They emphasized how the primary issues of insufficient foreign exchange reserves and the energy crisis had reduced industrial enterprises' output from 5.8% in Q1 2022 to 3% in Q2 2022. These difficulties had a significant impact on producers who already had to deal with an unfavorable working climate that had been made worse by the COVID-19 pandemic and the ongoing Russian-Ukrainian war. A negative impact was also seen on manufacturing variables like capacity utilization, contribution to real Gross Domestic Product (GDP), investment costs, employment expenses, and cost of production, among others. With limited foreign exchange inflow from crude oil sales, foreign exchange demand was pushed over the limit of supply, which contributed to the depreciation in the value of the naira. An increase in the cost of energy drove up global inflation figures, which had an impact on the cost of importation throughout the world, including in Nigeria (Anyafeoluwa, 2022).

Between January and June 2022, Nigerians received roughly \$10.11 billion in diaspora remittances, a 9.6% increase over the \$9.23 billion received during the same period in 2021. Nigeria's diaspora remittance inflows climbed slightly by 0.9% from \$10.02 billion in H2 2021 compared to H2 2021. According to data acquired from the CBN, this is the case. A total of \$23.3 million was recorded as remittances sent out of Nigeria during the reviewed period, which compares to a net inflow of \$10.09 billion in H1 2022 and net values of \$9.99 billion in H2 2021 and \$9.2 billion in the comparable period of 2021. 2022) CBN Reports. As the CBN's Naira4Dollar policy continues to encourage remittance inflows into the Nigerian economy, remittance inflows to Nigeria reached their highest level since the second quarter of 2019. Recall that the Naira 4 Dollar Scheme for diaspora remittances was announced by the apex bank in March 2021. For every dollar collected through the CBN International Money Remittance Operators, this plan provided receivers of remittances from the diaspora N5 (IMROs).

The plan, which was initially only supposed to continue for two months, was later made permanent. The COVID-19 outbreak and a decline in oil earnings, according to the CBN, had a detrimental influence on Africa's largest economy's foreign exchange market liquidity, which was intended to be maintained by the extension of the plan. The numbers are starting to recover from the decline brought on by the epidemic in 2020. A major boost for the Nigerian economy, which is in dire need of a foreign exchange, considering the sustained liquidity crunch and depreciation of the local currency is the phenomenal growth of diaspora remittances in recent times which has caught the attention of governments, particularly, in the developing countries, international organizations, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and the private sector, due to its importance as a viable source of external financing. Diaspora remittances have out-performed some other traditional capital inflows sources, such as, foreign direct and portfolio investments in several countries while it has also become a major source of foreign exchange for other countries. By its nature, diaspora remittances are countercyclical nature, voluntary and targeted at improving the welfare of members' family and their financial stability in their home countries. (Englama, 2007).

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian local currency tumbled by 0.12% at the I & EFX market on Thursday, December 02, 2022, a day after the World Bank (WB) reported that despite headwinds global remittance improvement of 5%, foreign currency exchange rates, and remittances into Nigeria were still slow down, falling to **N445.83** from N445.30 on Wednesday, December 01, 2022 prices on account of higher demand for foreign currencies by market participants. Contrarily, according to traders for the same period, the local currency increased 1.30% in the parallel market in the absence of speculative demand, from N765 to N755, decreasing the difference between official and parallel market rates. Numerous investment banking specialists have continuously held the view that the Nigerian Naira is somewhat overpriced and that the CBN is only delaying what must eventually happen. For instance, when the Naira closed that week at N445.33 versus the US Dollar, as of December 03, 2022, at the I & E foreign exchange window, the Naira had held steady against the US Dollar after spurious demand for foreign exchange that hit the system hard and fast following the decision to redesign the local currency (Alagbe, 2022).

The CBN's power to protect the Naira has been considerably weakened as a result, claims the investment firm, which has caused the official exchange rate to decline in the I&EFX window. The greenback rate has persisted at a large premium, 72.92%, over the official rates despite the fact that the official market foreign exchange prices have been reasonably constant thus far this year. We anticipate that when choosing to invest in Nigeria, foreign investors will continue to take difficulties with FX repatriation into account. Furthermore, we do not rule out the prospect of another Naira devaluation the following year in an effort to allow the currency rate to reflect present circumstances. The research question is when will the CBN devalue the Naira?. Most financial analysts believe that foreign exchange supply is likely to be more constricted over the coming years given the aforementioned factors and the expected 2023 Presidential election-related increase in demand for the US Dollars.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to empirically investigate the impact of our foreign exchange rate on our foreign exchange reserves and the diaspora remittances received in Nigeria for the period, 2015 – 2022. The specific objectives will be:

- a. To investigate the impact of foreign exchange rates (FER) on the foreign reserves (FOR) of Nigeria, for the period under review.
- b. To examine the impact of foreign exchange rates (FER) on diaspora remittances (DPR) of Nigeria, for the period under review.

Hypothesis of the Study

- a. Foreign exchange rates (FER) have no significant positive impact on the foreign reserves (FOR) of Nigeria, for the period under review.
- b. Foreign exchange rates (FER) have no significant positive impact on the foreign reserves (FOR) of Nigeria, for the period under review.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual framework

This section deals with the conceptual and theoretical reviews of the relevant literature in determining how foreign exchange rates have impacted the foreign reserves and diaspora remittances in Nigeria for the period, 2015 - 2022.

Foreign Exchange Rate:

An exchange rate is the value of one nation's currency for the purpose of conversion to the currency of another nation or economic zone. It can also be thought of as the value of one currency in comparison to another. The reference exchange rates and middle-market exchange rates are both based on ISO 4217:2015 (Codes for the representation of currencies), which outlines the format for a three-letter alphabetic code and three-digit numeric code that are given to each country's currency. 2020 (Chen and Scott). Transferring money internationally can be costly. Banks could charge up to 5% of the exchange rate in hidden fees and charges, for transferring money abroad, which makes diaspora remittances significantly costlier than expected. Most exchange rates are free floating and will rise or fall based on their supply and demand in the market. However, some currencies are not free floating as they have restrictions limiting their exchange to within their countries' borders. Also, a restricted currency can have its value set by the government. Spot rates, often known as cash values or market values, are one type of exchange rate that might exist. An exchange rate may also have a forward rate value, which is based on predictions of the currency's future movement relative to its current price. Changes in expectations for future interest rates in one country compared to another may cause forward rate values to shift. Let's imagine, for instance, that traders believe the Eurozone will loosen monetary policy in comparison to the United States. In this scenario, traders could purchase the dollar as opposed to the euro, causing the euro's value to decrease. Usually, the country currency it represents is abbreviated when quoting an exchange rate. 2020 (Chen and Scott).

Foreign Exchange Reserves

Assets held in reserve by a central bank in foreign currencies are known as foreign exchange reserves. These reserves support liabilities and have an impact on monetary policy. They consist of all foreign currency, bonds, treasury bills, and other government securities held by a central bank, such as the CBN. China is the largest holder of foreign exchange reserves worldwide, with the majority of them being kept in US dollars. The ideal way to retain foreign exchange reserves, according to economists, is in a currency that is not pegged to the nation's own currency. Africa Market Forces, 2022). Market Forces Africa is a media, research, and training platform that disseminates knowledge on the markets, economies, and investment environment. They choose news that covers a wide range of African markets in the economic, commercial, and financial technology sectors. Additionally, they have a presence in data analytics and special reports on businesses, individuals, and governments. Forex reserves, also known as foreign currency or exchange reserves, are made up of cash and other assets like gold that are kept by central banks and other financial institutions like the IMF. The central banks of nations maintain foreign exchange reserves for the following reasons:

To aid in maintaining a fixed rate for the value of a native currency. China, for instance, ties the value of the Yuan to the US Dollar. Stockpiling dollars increases the dollar's value against the yuan, which boosts sales by making Chinese exports less expensive than products created in the United States.

- i. To maintain a local currency below the US dollar. To keep the yen below the dollar, Japan, which has a floating exchange rate system, purchases US treasuries or bonds. This contributes to the continued affordability of its exports.
- ii. To retain liquidity in the event of a financial emergency.
- iii. To ensure that businesses may continue to import and export at a profit, a central bank can intervene and convert its foreign currency into local currency.
- iv. To meet a country's international finance obligations. These could include paying debts, financing imports and absorbing sudden capital movements.
- v. To support internal projects, see iii. Programs for industry or infrastructure can occasionally be funded in this way.
- vi. To comfort international investors. Investors who are frightened by war or internal upheaval may try to relocate their money elsewhere. Having foreign exchange reserves can reassure investors and provide them with a sense of security.
- vii. To spread out their holdings. A central bank can reduce risk by keeping a variety of currencies and assets in reserves and can be protected if one investment loses value.

Fig. 1. Countries with the largest foreign currency reserves in 2020.

Source: www.statista.com

The rate at which one currency will be exchanged for another is known as the exchange rate.

The majority of exchange rates are characterized as floating and fluctuate in response to market supply and demand. Some exchange rates are set or linked to the value of the currency of a particular nation. Exchange rate fluctuations have an impact on businesses by altering the cost of supplies imported from other nations and the demand for their goods among clients abroad. (2012) (Investopedia).

Why the Dollar is a Safe Haven in Times of Economic Crisis?

Investors and currency traders frequently try to protect themselves by converting their cash holdings into so-called "safe haven" currencies during unstable times for the global economy. Safe-haven assets include currencies like the

US dollar, the Swiss franc, the Japanese yen, and others. Given that it serves as the world's reserve currency and is frequently used in cross-border transactions, the dollar is particularly alluring. The largest gold reserves in the world serve as additional security. When compared to the major competing currencies, the so-called "Greenback" recently reached its greatest level in twenty years. Due to indications that the US Federal Reserve would raise interest rates more quickly than most, investors have started pouring money into it. Banknotes, deposits, bonds, treasury bills, and other types of government securities can all be included in foreign exchange reserves.

- i. Although these assets have multiple uses, they are primarily kept as a safety net in case a central government agency's home currency depreciates sharply or goes bankrupt.
- ii. Holding a sizable quantity of foreign exchange reserves by a central bank is a widespread practice in nations all over the world. Since the dollar is the most traded currency globally, the majority of these reserves are stored in this currency.
- iii. The British pound (GBP), the euro (EUR), the Chinese yuan (CNY), or the Japanese yen (JPY) may also be included in the foreign exchange reserves. (2012) (Investopedia).

Diaspora Remittances:

Diaspora remittance is the inflow and the most favourable outcome of migration. A remittance is money sent by a person in a foreign land to his or her home country. So, every time an expert sends money home, they make a direct contribution to the agendas of their national economic development classified as a diaspora remittance. Every unit of currency remitted to the country goes towards feeding a stomach, saving a life, or igniting a mind.

Due to the huge sums involved, remittances are now being recognised as an important contributor to the country's growth and development. Workers' remittances are recorded under the current transfers in the current account of the balance of payments. They include goods and financial instruments transferred by migrants, who reside and work abroad in a given country for more than one year. It could be in cash or in kind from migrant to resident households in the country of origin. Migrant transfers are treated as capital transfers of financial assets as they move from one country to another and stay for more than one year. (Tewelde, 2005).

Fig. 2: Nigeria Diaspora Remittance Inflow

Source: Nairalytics, November 11, 2022

Migration

Migration is the voluntary movement of persons from a home country to foreign country to seek for a more prosperous environment, to work, or to ensure the safety of life. When migration is documented, it is termed

regular, the reverse is termed irregular migration. Human trafficking is not migration because people are forced to move against their will. (Englama, 2007). Fundamentally, the theories of migration take into cognizance the various labour market opportunities available in developing countries. The theoretical underpinnings are of those individuals who choose employments that maximize their expected gains from migration. The labour-force, both actual and potential, compare expected incomes for a given horizon in the labour receiving country with the domestic incomes and recommend migration if the former exceeds the latter (Todaro, 1969).

Remittance is the inflow that results from migration and the most favorable outcome of migration is diaspora remittances. Financial remittances are the inflow of cash and financial products. Cash is usually sent formally through the banks and the networks of International Money Transfer Operators (IMTOs) and can also be conveyed through informal channels. Financial remittances could also be in the form of diaspora bond receipts that are designed by the home countries to attract funds from the diaspora.

Impact of Diaspora Remittances on the Nigerian Economy

The massive brain drain, auspiciously targeting diaspora remittances, currently ravaging the Nigerian corporate world is leaving a huge skill gap in most organizations, as it seems the best hands are the ones jumping on the “*Japa*” trend, making an imperative case for firms to train and retrain their staff to fill the spaces. Additionally, this has increased competitiveness in the hiring process as businesses increasingly devise plans to outsmart one another and secure the last remaining top talent in the sector. The tremendous intellectual flight currently being observed in Nigeria is being aided by the ongoing strikes by public universities in that nation. Along with the economic problems, the African behemoth is being torn apart by insecurity, poor living conditions, and a lack of access to appropriate infrastructure.

In order to attract investments, develop a more robust educational system free of strike actions, and eventually become a destination for international students to study in, it is crucial that the Nigerian government improve the quality of public education in Nigeria while allowing more private players to operate in the sector. In order to accommodate workers who wish to work part-time or from remote places, some businesses have had to adopt a more flexible work environment. Spending on international education necessitates the availability of foreign cash, which the Nigerian economy now lacks. The local currency has significantly depreciated in value relative to the US Dollar as a result of the increased demand for the currency to pay for imports, speculative needs, and international services, among other things. The official currency rate hit a record low of N437.5/\$1 on Wednesday, September 5, 2022, according to the Nairalytics exchange rate tracker, which can be viewed here.

This represents a N21/\$ drop when compared to the average of N416/\$1 recorded in the previous year. It is interesting to note that the CBN's frequent intervention, which has limited the country's foreign reserve and caused it to lose more than \$2 billion so far this year, is the sole reason the official exchange rate is so stable. The exchange rate has experienced severe fluctuations in the black market, trading as low as N730/\$1, a loss of N165/\$1 from the N565/\$1 recorded at the start of the year. a downturn fueled by escalating demand, speculative activity, and insufficient supply. When there is an insufficient supply of foreign currency, higher foreign exchange spending has the effect of increasing the pressure on the exchange rate, which devalues the local currency (CBN Reports, 2022).

However, since they started disbursing dollars via cards, commercial banks have demanded that travelers in need of dollars for Personal Travel Allowance (PTA) and Business Travel Allowance (BTA) use travel debit cards. a step taken to stop passengers from misusing their free forex by not using it for travel-related expenses. This is in response to some banks' ongoing inability to meet the demand for foreign exchange from visitors. It is important to keep in mind that when Nigerians go to other countries, they aid in the development of the host nation while leaving a sizable hole in the economy of their home country. In the meantime, some Nigerians who do not now have the financial resources to travel overseas are preparing themselves by enrolling in online courses offered by international colleges.

Theoretical Framework

Rapoport and Docquier (2005) provided an excellent overview of theoretical reasons for remitting money home. Accordingly, remittances are sent home due to a combination of altruistic and self-interest motives. It has been widely acknowledged that altruism towards family members at home has become an important motivation for remitting diaspora remittances. (Lucas and Stark 1985).

This implies that remittances are simply a utility function in which the migrant cares about the consumption of the other members of the households. On the other hand, self-interest motives for remitting may evolve, if the family aims at entering into mutually beneficial agreements thereby making the family to be eligible for inheritance, esteem or other resources in the country of origin. In this respect, migrants send remittances in order to reimburse the household for past expenditures such as schooling or costs directly related to migration or investments for the future either out of concern for inheritance or as a way of maintaining status or return home in dignity. Other intimidating credentials relating to the rising diaspora remittances to Nigeria are appropriately captured and depicted below:

- i. Nigeria has made a conscious effort to take steps to entice remittance inflows that will support economic growth. Some of the few initiatives in that direction include the issuance of a \$300 million Nigerian diaspora bond and the implementation of a Certificate of Capital Importation (CCI) policy in 2018.
- ii. The CCI, issued by Nigerian banks, permits straight-through processing and certifies an influx of foreign currency in the form of cash or products.
- iii. Nigeria has now joined the International Association of Money Transfer Networks, among other organizations. However, many scholars and economic experts are still perplexed as to why Nigeria is not the top-ranked African nation for remittances from the diaspora despite these alarming numbers. The explanation comes not only in the dedication and responsibility Nigerian experts demonstrate by sending regular remittances to their families in the diaspora but also in the unfavorable currency rates and accompanying costs of cashing these remittances.

Empirical Review

Studies have shown that several factors influence the decision to remit money from abroad. One such factor is the prevailing economic circumstance in the country of origin. Other factors include: wage rates, exchange rates, inflation rate, socio-demographic characteristics of migrants, political, economic, and legal environment of the home country of remitters are part of the factors worthy consideration. Furthermore, Strong cultural behavior and emotional links to the migrants' home of origin are also critical. Although several developing countries such as Mexico, India, the Philippines, etc., had long taken advantage of diaspora remittance to boost their economic growth, others such as Nigeria are beginning to recognize the need to enhance the inflow of diaspora remittances (Russell,1986).

Researchers have not agreed on the role of diaspora remittance as an economic development tool as some have expressed concern that continued currency appreciation due to high inflows could lead to a Dutch disease

phenomenon. On the other hand, there are examples of countries that made deliberate efforts to attract remittances as a source of external financing. It is against this background that this paper examines the impact of foreign exchange rates on the foreign reserves and diaspora remittances on Nigerian family financial stability (Englama, 2007).

It is possible to draw the conclusion that the increase in remittances to Nigeria is partially a result of the expansion of the global economy, particularly in high-income OECD nations, as well as the rise in oil prices since July 2017 that has boosted economic activity in countries that produce oil. The presence of Nigerian professionals in OECD and oil-producing nations, who frequently remit money to their loved ones back home, may play a key role in the remittance flows to Nigeria (Chen and Scott, 2020).

Micro economic studies by El Sakka and McNabb (1999), Rusell (1986) identified determinants of diaspora remittances to include such factors as the: level of economic activity in the host and the home countries, the wage rate, inflation, exchange rate, interest rate differentials or the efficiency of the banking system as contributory factors to remittance flows in countries.

Also stressed in one of the studies conducted by Wahba (1991) on the factors influencing diaspora remittances, he stated that the prevailing economic circumstance in the country of origin coupled with political stability and consistency in government policies and financial intermediation significantly affect the flow of diaspora remittances.

Faini (1994) in his study found evidence that the real exchange rate is also a significant determinant of diaspora remittances. Real earnings of workers as well as total number of migrants in the host countries were consistently found to have a significant and positive effect on the flow of diaspora remittances (Swamy 1981; Straubhaar, 1986; Elbadawi and Rocha, 1992). Socio-demographic characteristics of migrants, where female migrants are more likely to have families with them in the host country, impact on their capabilities to remit money as diaspora remittances home. However, social factors by way of strong cultural behaviour and emotional links to the migrants' home of origin are also critical in remittances decision-making process (Faini, 1994).

Methodology

The **ex post facto** type of research design is adopted in this study since all the data used for analysis have been published in the CBN website and there is no attempt to manipulate or control these variables, obviously, because these variables cannot be manipulated. Using a detailed panel-level data set, this study extends previous researchers' works on this field by adopting a full multiple regression model in analyzing the dependent variable herewith proxy by the quarterly foreign exchange rates on the independent variables external reserves and the quarterly diaspora remittances as gathered from the CBN website. The dependent variable (**Y**) which is foreign exchange rates (**FER**) in Nigeria for the period, January, 2015 – December, 2022 and the two independent variables **X1, X2** are proxied by the absolute quarterly values of foreign reserves (**FOR**) and the absolute quarterly values of diaspora remittances (**DPR**) respectively.

Intervening or Moderating Variable

Onwumere (2005) defines intervening variables as those variables whose values are lying or falling between the dependent and independent variables in a multiple regression equation at any particular point in time. These variables theoretically affect the observed phenomenon but have not been selected, measured or manipulated as independent variables in the course of the research. The effect of the intervening or moderating variables must merely be inferred from the effects of the other selected independent variables on the dependent variable used in the regression equation.

The Migration and Development Brief 33, published by the World Bank and the Global Knowledge Partnership (Knomad, 2019) had already propounded that, Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) countries, like Nigeria are among the costliest countries in the region to send diaspora remittances to. They projected that sending remittances to Nigeria costs an average of 9% in 2019 and 8.5% in 2020. We adopted these statistics to build a model for calculating our intervening variable, **U**– Cost of Remittance (**COR**) which is the associated costs of collecting diaspora remittances in Nigeria for the period 2015 – 2022 with the following extrapolated estimated rates:

Table 1: Applicable Costs Rates

Year	Costs
17-Nov-15	5.55%
17-Dec-16	6.35%
31-Dec-17	6.85%
31-Dec-18	7.55%
30-Dec-19	8.95%
17-Dec-20	9.05%
17-Dec-21	9.25%
17-Nov-22	9.50%

Fig. 3. Associated Costs of Collecting Diaspora Remittance.

Source: Author's Research

International Money Transfers Operators (IMTO) like Express Money and Western Union money transfers are working hard to bring down the cost of diaspora remittances in line with the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which recommended 3% for transfer fee and currency conversion. Presently, the average global cost of sending money is about 9.50% as of the last quarter of 2022. Therefore, a sure way to test the impact of our foreign exchange rate on external reserves and diaspora remittances is to adopt the associated costs of collecting these remittances as the intervening variable. Actually, this stochastic term U introduced into the multiple regression model serves as a proxy for all the other intervening variables that may have been omitted from the model but which may collectively affect the dependent variable as used in this study.

According to Gujarati (1995), it is important to include this stochastic error term (U) in our model because its inclusion captures the vagueness of our theory, accounts for the unavailability of some data, accounts for the dichotomy of core variables versus peripheral variables and the principles of parsimony, that is, trying to keep our regression model as simple as possible. From the above limitations of a multiple regression analysis model, we can ascertain that there may be perfect multi-co linearity in the regression model if adopted.

Techniques for Data Analysis

The main technique to be employed in this study is the Ordinary Least Square Method (OLS) - Multiple Regression analysis tools. This statistical technique is used in measuring the impact of one or more independent variables on a dependent variable. It can also be used in describing the nature of relationship that exists between the variables by expressing that relationship in a mathematical form (Onwumere, 2005).

In other words, multiple regression analysis provides an estimation model which expresses the functional relationship between the dependent variable (Y) and the independent variables (X). Again, when intervening variables are included in the multiple regression equation, then we can appropriately formulate a regression model. Therefore, the multiple regression models to be adopted in this study is stated as follows:

$$Y = \alpha_0 + X_1 FER + X_2 DPR + U_t$$

Where:

Y = Dependent Variable, proxy by Foreign Exchange Rates (FER)

α_0 = Constant of the regression equation

X_1 = Coefficient of the independent variable, Foreign External Reserves (FOR).

X_2 = Coefficient of the independent variable, Diaspora Remittances (DPR).

U_t = Intervening/Moderating Variable/Error term, Costs of Collecting Remittance (COR).

Theoretically, the coefficients of the independent variables will take the following a priori expectations.

FER>0, FOR>0, DPR>0

Multiple regression analysis is usually deployed to resolve the problem of predicting the average values of one or more other variables when there is a known variable. This implies that the values of the independent variables can be estimated or predicted from knowing the value of the dependent variable. R^2 which is the Coefficient of Determination tests for the proportion of the variation in the dependent variable that can be attributed to the variations of the independent variables. R^2 therefore, usually lies between 0 and 1; $0 \leq R^2 \leq 1$, meaning that R^2 cannot be zero. The closer it is to 1 the better the goodness of fit.

Results and Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics which presents the mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, as well as jarque-bera goodness of fit tests are shown in this analysis. The usual results expected are noted. Results of standard deviation which measures dispersion from the mean, indicates wide variation from the centre (mean) because the data variegated remittance from Nigerians in diaspora at different times between January, 2015 and December 2022, on monthly basis, making it 70 end points data observations used for the analysis, which also makes it a bit difficult to accurately predict the data. The skewness and kurtosis statistics which are measures of the departure from symmetry and peakedness of the distribution respectively show positive skewness as the data collected are majorly and quantitatively high, which also justifies the high level of peakedness. The Jarque-Bera goodness of fit test may not follow normal distribution since there is no uniformity in the data collected from various sources: Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Federal Ministry of Statistics, (FMS) and the Federal Ministry of Finance (FMF). The descriptive statistics results are as shown in table 2 below

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics Result

	FER	FOR	DPR
Mean	14262.3	2414.24	19242.63
Median	45281.00	40262.00	13137.00
Maximum	568499.0	91250.00	91467.00
Minimum	1470.00	1368.000	2015.000
Std. Dev.	173691.3	29021.43	20555.40
Skewness	1.456806	1.597227	1.874163
Kurtosis	3.575421	3.521313	7.128300
Jarque-Bera	14.61003	16.35123	35.89154
Probability	0.001007	0.001172	0.000000
Sum	4968148.	917758.0	708745.0
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.00E+11	1.81E+11	1.58E+10
Observations	32	32	32

Source: Author's computation

Results of standard deviation which measures dispersion from the mean variables indicate a wide variation from the centre (mean) which implies a high volatile nature of the data set which is an indication that these variables cannot be easily predicted. The skewness and kurtosis statistics which are measures of the departure from symmetry and peakedness of the distribution respectively, show that the data series in all the variables are positively skewed and with excess kurtosis ($K > 3$). The Jarque-Bera goodness of fit test with probability values less than 0.05 implies that the series do not follow normal distribution.

Time Series Econometrics

Most economic time series data like the panel data adopted in this research usually exhibit trend influence, in other words, they trend up and down as economic climate changes. For example, in times of boom, most economic trends like, diaspora remittance, foreign exchange reserves, gross domestic product, investments, employment, etc. will be rising while during recession there will be a decrease in these trends meaning that most of these economic time series variables are not stationary. In other words, they suffer from **Unit root** problems and when we run multiple

regression analysis without first resolving the unit root problems, we may jump into erroneous conclusions that all the estimates are significant, whereas, the statistical significance of the variables analyzed may not be as a result of any meaningful relationship existing between the variables but just as a result of trend. When we regress non stationary time series variables on other non-stationary time series variables, we often produce spurious regression results whose policy recommendations, if applied to the economy becomes misleading. To avoid such spurious regression, it is necessary to first examine the time series properties of these variables, such properties include doing a stationary or unit root test, co-integration test (where it is positive) adopt and error correction model (ECM) test to address it.

Test for Stationary or Unit Root Issues

This test is conducted to find out whether a time series data has unit root issues or not. There are so many procedures for testing for unit root but in this study, we shall be adopting the **Augmented Dickey Fuller Test (ADF)** model, which involves estimating the equation:

$$\Delta Y_t = \beta_1 + \beta_2 t + \beta_3 t^2 + \sigma Y_{t-2} + \sigma Y_{t-1} + \sum \alpha \Delta Y_{t-1} + U_t$$

Where:

Y_t = Time Series Variable.

t = Time Trend.

Δ = First Difference Operator.

The essence of the ADF test is to ensure that none of the variables adopted in this study possess non-stationary variables and the decision rule in analyzing the multiple regression equations will be to **reject** the null hypothesis if the ADF statistic is greater than the Mackinnon critical value in absolute terms and **accept** the alternative hypothesis at levels. If all the time series variables are stationary at levels, the series is considered to be stable.

Table 3: Summary of ADF Unit root test

Variable	ADF-Stat	C.V @5%	p-value	Order of integration	Inference
L FER	-5.70	-3.44	0.0003	I(1)	Stationary
L FOR	-5.44	-3.55	0.0006	I(0)	Stationary
L DPR	-5.62	-3.22	0.0004	I(0)	Stationary

Source: Author's Extract from E-Views 9.0 output

Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend

Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=9)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.335137	0.0005
Test critical values:		
1% level	-4.3348726	
5% level	-3.440325	
10% level	-3.402243	

***MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.**

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit root test established where the series of the variables are stationary. That is, where they have constant mean and variance. From the result, FOR and DPR were stationary at first differencing while FER is stationary at the first level of integration. This combination of order of integration of zero and 1 confirms that OLS – multiple regression models is **not very suitable** for this nature of analysis, instead we adopt the **Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL)** bound tests which accommodates all the variables at order 0 and 1 at the same time. ARDL is a dynamic model while OLS is static model.

Table 4 ARDL Bound test result

Dependent Variable: L FER; Sample (adjusted): 2015 -2022 :

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC);

Number of models evaluated: 12400

Selected Model: ARDL (3, 3, 3,)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
L FER(-3)	-1.633650	0.312859	-5.30066	0.0124
L DPR(-3)	0.587031	0.095056	5.901300	0.0111
L FOR(-3)	-0.395835	0.088051	-3.775844	0.0151
C	9.474307	2.575642	3.440553	0.0333

R-squared = 0.878 000**Adjusted R-squared = 0.848 114****F-statistic = 132. 944****Prob.(F-statistic) = 0.001022****Durbin-Watson Stat. = 2.295110****Source: Researcher's extract from Eviews result (2021)**

Results of the ARDL bound test are as presented in the table above. The Adjusted R-squared value of **0.848** (84.8%) indicates that there is no much variations after adjusting for degrees of freedom. The Durbin-Watson statistic value of 2.295110 indicates that the model is free from first order autocorrelation problem. So our multiple regression equation:

$$Y = \alpha_0 + X_1DPR + X_2FOR + U_t$$

$$FER_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1DPR_t - \beta_2FOR_t + \mu_t$$

$$-1.64 = 9.474 + 0.587DPR - 0.396FOR$$

can now be restated as:

which can be translated into:

Table 5 ARDL Bound Test Result

Sample: 2015 - 2022; Included observations: 32

Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	5.777222	5

Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.26	3.35
5%	2.62	3.79
2.5%	2.96	4.18
1%	3.41	4.68

Source: Researcher's extract from Eviews result (2022)

This shows that only diaspora remittances (DPR) have a positive relationship with foreign exchange rates (FER) proxied by quarterly diaspora remittances, while foreign exchange reserves (FOR) show a negative impact on FER which appropriately meets our a-priori expectations. From the ARDL result, lag 3 for all the variables were chosen. The ARDL (3,3,3) result indicates that controlling for other explanatory variables in the model, L DPR with a coefficient value of 0.587, t-statistic value of 5.901 and associated probability value of $0.0111 < 0.05$ has a significant positive effect on FER; L FOR has a negative and insignificant effect on FER (Coefficient = -0.395; t statistic = -3.776 and p-value = $0.0151 < 0.05$). This indicates that Foreign Exchange Rates have **mixed** effect on our Foreign Reserves and Diaspora Remittances in Nigeria for the period, 2015 -2022. The R^2 value of 0.899 indicates that the model is a good one since about **89.9%** of the total variations in FER in Nigeria are attributable to Diaspora Remittance (DPR) and Foreign Exchange Reserves (FOR) Only 0.11% of the total variations are unexplained in this model could be due to other extraneous variables not considered in this study.

The ARDL bound test result with F-statistic = 5.777 > 5 upper bound critical values at 10% 5% 2.5% and 1% respectively confirms that there is a long-run relationship between foreign exchange rates and diaspora remittances in Nigeria.

Ramsey Reset Test

The researcher also performed this test to ascertain whether there is a functional form misspecification in the ARDL regression model adopted in this study. The hypotheses are stated as follows:

Hypothesis: H_0 : The model is correctly specified

H_1 : The model is wrongly specified

Decision Rule: Reject H_0 if Prob. (F-statistic) ≤ 0.05 ; otherwise do not reject

Table 6 Ramsey RESET Test

Omitted Variables: Squares of fitted values

	Value	Df	Probability
t-statistic	0.786441	2	0.5251
F-statistic	0.608924	(1, 2)	0.5251

Source: Researcher's Extract from Eviews Result (See Appendix C)

The Ramsey Regression Error Specification test with $F(1, 2) = 0.608924$ and associated probability value of $0.5251 > 0.05$ indicates that the model is correctly specified which implies that there is no functional form problem in the model. Of which course, the explanatory variables have significant power in explaining the response variables in the regression model.

Discussion of Findings

The Foreign Exchange Rates (FER) used the dependent variable in this study has a coefficient value of -1.634, t-statistic value of -5.3006 and associated probability value of $0.0124 < 0.05$ which is a negative and insignificant impact on the independent variables used. This indicates that foreign exchange reserves and diaspora remittance indices have a mixed effect on exchange rates (FER) in Nigeria for the period, January, 2015 – December, 2022. This finding is in agreement with Wahba (1991) who hold the view that the factors influencing diaspora remittances include the prevailing economic circumstance in the country of origin coupled with political stability, consistency in government policies and financial intermediation which significantly affect the flow of diaspora remittances and Faini (1994) who in his study found evidence that the real exchange rate is also a significant determinant of diaspora remittances.

Furthermore, Foreign Exchange Reserves (FOR) has a negative and insignificant effect on foreign exchange rates Its coefficient of variation is -0.395, t-statistic value of -3.776 and associated probability value of $0.0151 < 0.05$ which is a negative and insignificant impact, while Diaspora Remittances (DPR) have a positive but insignificant impact on foreign exchange rates with its coefficient of variation is 0.587, t-statistic value of 5.901 and associated probability value of $0.0111 < 0.05$.

R^2 which measures the coefficient of determination of the model has a value of 0.878 (about 87.8%) which indicates that the ARDL model adopted in this study is a good one since about 87.8% of the total variations in foreign exchange rates (FER) can be explained by the variations in foreign exchange reserves and diaspora remittances movements. The Adjusted R-squared value of 0.848 (84.8 %) indicates that there is no much variations after adjustment for the degrees of freedom in the model. Only 12.2% of the total variations are unexplained in the model and these can be attributable to other intervening/moderating variables not included in the model.

The F- statistic value which measures the overall significance of the model is indicated as 132.94 which means the both explanatory variables taken together significantly passed the overall significance test at 5% and 1% level of significance. This implies that the linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables that was previously hypothesized can now be sustained. The Durbin-Watson statistic value of $2.295 < 3$ indicates that the ARDL model adopted here is free from first order autocorrelation problems.

Summary of Findings

In this section, we consider a summary of our research findings which have supported the policy recommendations made above to all the relevant stakeholders identified in our significance of this study. We summarize that:

- a. The Foreign Exchange Rates (FER) used the dependent variable in this study has a coefficient value of -1.634, t-statistic value of -5.3006 and associated probability value of $0.0124 < 0.05$ which is a negative and insignificant impact on the independent variables used. This indicates that foreign exchange reserves and diaspora remittance indices have a mixed effect on exchange rates (FER) in Nigeria for the period, January, 2015 – December, 2022. This finding is in agreement with Wahba (1991) who hold the view that the factors influencing diaspora remittances include the prevailing economic circumstance in the country of origin coupled with political stability, consistency in government policies and financial intermediation which significantly affect the flow of diaspora remittances and Faini (1994) who in his study found evidence that the real exchange rate is also a significant determinant of diaspora remittances.
- b. Foreign Exchange Reserves (FOR) has a negative and insignificant effect on foreign exchange rates, its coefficient of variation is -0.395, t-statistic value of -3.776 and associated probability value of $0.0151 < 0.05$ which has a negative and insignificant impact, while Diaspora Remittances (DPR) have a positive but insignificant impact on foreign exchange rates with its coefficient of variation as 0.587, t-statistic value of 5.901 and associated probability value of $0.0111 < 0.05$.

Conclusion

As of December 09, 2022 the Naira closed flat at **N446** as per US Dollar at the I&E foreign exchange market window amidst expectations that FX Inflows will rise this last quarter of the year. Contrary to expectations, the CBN is unlikely to devalue the Naira in the short term. Meanwhile, the Nigerian economy will experience FX liquidity tightness as oil prices begin to moderate, though with a positive outlook given that the nation's oil production volume has improved, according to data from OPEC. Foreign portfolio investors will remain aloof, according to analysts, saying Nigeria is unlikely to attract foreign investors till mid-year in 2023 due to election uncertainties. At the Bankers' Committee meeting held in Lagos recently, the CBN Governor maintained that exports repatriation from rebates will rise to \$1 billion via the window. Foreign currency inflows have been in downbeat mode amidst uncertainties in the Nigerian macroeconomics environment. Due to these uncertainties, we believe that the 2023 election remains a downside for foreign exchange inflows.

Recommendations

The impact of foreign exchange rates on external reserves and diaspora remittances hinges more on the sustainability of the inflows as well as the development of appropriate structures to channel these inflows into areas that would be beneficial to the economy as a whole. The following policy measures are therefore recommended for implementation, if external reserves and diaspora remittances will help to stabilize the financial position of Nigerian families and impact on the economic development of the country in general:

- a. The apex regulatory institution in Nigeria (CBN) should ensure the involvement of larger numbers of banks and other financial institutions in the inward transfer of diaspora remittances. Some countries such as Senegal have opened domestic bank branches in other countries with a high migrant population. This has increased inflows as migrants prefer to deal with domestic institutions and staff. At the home front, there should be increased access to banking service points to increase the number of recipients that would have easy access to receiving their funds. Government should also ensure that the entire regulatory and supervisory framework of the CBN is overhauled and strengthened to encourage the participation of more International Money Transfer Operators (IMTOs) through good corporate governance policies and ensuring adequate risk management practices. They should be regularly revising and approving the list of accredited IMTOs, as the last one was done via the CBN circular of November 09, 2016. The various channels of informal inflow of remittances to Nigeria can be formalized by ensuring that all large or significant amounts of informal remittances are channelled to the formal channels. This could be achieved by permitting post offices and micro finance institutions to operate in money transfer businesses, as they have more branches and presence in the rural areas of the country. Both recommendations would reduce the cost of collecting these remittances and also increase the efficiency of remittance delivery.
- b. There is need for **devaluation** of the local currency since the Naira is presently **20%** above its fair value

measurement using the CBN real effective exchange rate. Three indicators the CBN widely uses are the black-market rate, the CBN's real effective exchange rate, and the currency fair value rate. Analysts believe there is hope for the foreign exchange rate to weaken by an equivalent amount over the next six-nine months, taking it to as high as N520/\$.

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